

THE ESSENCE AND IMPORTANCE OF MATERIAL AND SOCIAL SUPPORT FOR MILITARY FOLLOWERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439864>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 04th December 2022

Accepted: 14th December 2022

Online: 15th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Logistics support, logistics system, support of military units, outsourcing of logistics operations, resource potential of military logistics.

ABSTRACT

«The logistical support system elements for the preparedness for military operations». The modern views of the essence and content of logistics support for the preparedness for military operations for military logisticians and academic experts differ in some way. The main differences in the views of the authors are based on defining the boundaries of the logistics system. In particular, military traditions significantly narrow the field of logistics management of the processes of providing structural units under certain conditions. At the same time, approaches to the organization of logistical support of rear structures and units that perform military operations are different algorithms. On the contrary, according to the academic vision, the logistics of military units is only part of the macro-logistics system. That is why the purpose of this study is to search a science-based system of supporting of all participants in the logistics chain for the preparedness for military operations. The implementation project of key elements of the logistical support system of readiness of the armed forces units for military operations is offered. The implementation of these proposals is expected to achieve a synergistic effect, namely: a powerful reduction in time, which is very critical in terms of active military operations; achieving high quality of logistic support operations; reducing the prime cost of operations, especially one-time or functionally unacceptable for military units; quick reaction to change of conditions, etc. Such results can accelerate the practical implementation of NATO standards in the armed forces.

Introduction. Modern military-political Ukrainian realities require the formation of a single effective logistic support system of military units. The main strategic goals of

our country must correlate with NATO logistics standards and instructions. So it's very important to search a science-based system of supporting of all participants in

the logistics chain for the preparedness for military operations. Analysis of recent researches and publications. Modern scientific publications contain a large amount of material devoted to the logistic support of different activities. The article [4] explained the content of the term "logistics of the defense sector". This topic has also gained popularity in the military sphere. In particular, in June 2020 took place Scientific and practical webinar on the topic "Improving the logistics of the Armed Forces of Ukraine based on the experience of the joint forces operation" in the National University of Defense of Ukraine named after I. Chernyakhovsky. Most of the reports were based on the principles of the NATO logistics experience. There is interpretation of the terms "logistic support", "material and technical support", "logistics management bodies", "forces and means of logistics" in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers [10]. So, logistic support is a complex of "measures from: logistic support planning; identification of armaments needs, special and vehicles, combat (military and special) equipment, material and technical means and services; design, development (modernization and modification) of armaments, military and special equipment and logistical means, their purchase, supply, storage, repair, maintenance, operation control; sale, write-off and utilization of surplus weapons, military and special equipment and material and technical means; planning and implementation of military transportation by all modes of transport; purchase of works and services of bath and laundry, trade and household services; catering; quartering of troops (forces, bodies); procurement or construction, maintenance, operation of military infrastructure".

The material and technical means include: "missiles, ammunition, military equipment, fuel, special liquids, food, belongings, medical and other property, in addition to real estate, which are necessary

to ensure the components of the defense forces in the performance of their defense tasks, protection of its sovereignty, territorial integrity and inviolability". Logistics support bodies are "military management bodies (management bodies) of the Armed Forces, other military formations, of the law enforcement and intelligence agencies, the State Special Communications, the State Emergency Service, which are authorized by law to provide tasks for logistic support". The forces and means of logistic support are: "arsenals, bases, support centers, warehouses, automobile and repair and restoration military units (subdivisions) of the Armed Forces, other components of the defense forces, which are designed to maintain stockpiles of weapons, military and special equipment, material and technical means, their transportation, maintenance and repair". In particular, in the NATO Logistics Handbook (1997) we read "the definition of logistics by NATO covers a wide range of responsibilities that fall into different areas of the NATO organization". NATO logistics is largely identified with the concept of logistic supporting. So NATO Logistics Handbook offers the two aspects of logistics have to do with the relationship between the producer and the consumer, and two additional aspects that have to do with how logistics functions are performed [8]: - Cooperative Logistics is the totality of bilateral and multilateral consumer and production logistics arrangements to optimize in a coordinated and rationalized way, logistics support to NATO forces. The aim of NATO Cooperative Logistics is to achieve cost savings through economy of scale and increased efficiency in peacetime, crisis and wartime logistics support. Development of NATO Cooperative Logistics arrangements is largely facilitated by the use of NATO Production and Logistics Organizations (NPLOs), particularly the NATO Maintenance and Supply Agency (NAMSA) using modern

techniques in the field of materiel management and procurement. Multinational Logistics must function as an effective force multiplier. With the risk now Omni-directional, the diminishing logistic support resources, and the principle of shared logistics responsibilities, the evolution toward multinational logistics becomes of utmost importance. It is proposed that this term cover: "The different means to logistically support operations other than purely national, such as multinational integrated logistic support, role specialization support and lead nation support".

Thus, according to NATO logistics as logistics supporting is in fact material and technical supporting for the defense sector. The same interpretation and content of logistics is followed by Ukrainian military logisticians. The basic principles on which the logistical support of the defense forces is based during their preparation and application are:

- centralization of management to achieve effective implementation of tasks to meet the common needs of the components of the defense forces with the involvement of all available forces and means of logistical support of the defense forces components, taking into account their capabilities, as well as the efficient use of available resources;

- priority and sufficiency of logistical support for continuous and full satisfaction of the needs of the defense forces components in armaments, military and special equipment, material and technical means, as well as directing the main efforts of logistic support by the priority tasks performed by the defense forces during their preparation and the application;

- joint implementation of tasks to meet the needs of the defense forces by the joint efforts of central executive bodies, other state bodies, forces and means of which are involved in the defense forces, the Armed Forces, other defense forces, taking into account their capabilities;

- interaction and coordination of actions between of the defense forces components and central (local) executive bodies, local governments, other state bodies, enterprises of the defense industry, other enterprises, institutions and organizations, regardless of ownership, on the provision of weapons, military and special equipment, material and technical means and services during the training of defense forces and during their application;

- functional compatibility of organizational structures of management bodies of logistical support of defense forces components and the forces and means subordinated to them;

- cooperation of the constituent forces of the defense with the bodies of foreign states, international organizations and the armed forces of other states in matters of providing the constituent forces of the defense with material means and services during their preparation and application in accordance with the powers defined by law. The speakers of Scientific and practical webinar somewhat clarified the above principles of logistical support of the rear and troops in operations. Emphasis was placed on the efficiency of the use of the received military property / services and infrastructure facilities, the flexibility of processes and the stability of logistical support as well as of the possibility of integrating the logistics system of the Armed Forces of Ukraine or its individual elements during joint operations with the armed forces of NATO member states. The last thesis brings logistical support to the macro level. Military logisticians define the ultimate goal of logistics as the acquisition by the Armed Forces of Ukraine of such qualities that will ensure the ability in peacetime to ensure the combat and mobilization readiness of forces in their new form. And in wartime, the ultimate goal of logistics is to increase their combat capabilities at all levels of armed struggle: strategic, operational, and tactical. So the essence of improving the provision by

military property to forces services of in peacetime with the introduction of logistics in the Armed Forces of Ukraine is the need of:

- reviewing the functions of the elements of the military property supply system and the system as a whole;

- identifying the priority, sufficiency and redundancy or duplication of supplies;

- transition to new organizational and staffing structures, to build a vertical of their management, a system of staffing and training of services included in the logistics system;

- development of modern approaches to the accumulation, structure and use of military stockpiles, organization of military transportation and evacuation, technical equipment (military units and subdivisions, institutions and medical establishments);

- improvement of economic activity, quality of planning, efficiency of infrastructure operation;

- optimization of costs for the purchase and provision of services, etc. In the context of European integration and new tasks of the Armed Forces of Ukraine related to Ukraine's participation in environmental protection, anti-terrorist operation, peacekeeping activities under the auspices of NATO and the UN, webinar participants stressed the need to reform troops (forces), types of logistics, technical and medical support in accordance with NATO standards. In this context, the organization of logistics management is to create an appropriate management system, maintaining any level of its readiness, building and ensuring the smooth carrying operations (combat operations). In addition, they formulated the main transformation directions of the existing system of military property and services of the Ukrainian Armed Forces, such as: complete change of all rules and procedures of procurement, introduction of electronic procurement and electronic document flow. This, according to military

logisticians, will contribute to the creation of an effective logistics system of the Ukrainian Armed Forces, capable of planning and managing the processes of logistics of troops (forces) both in peacetime and in special periods and will be compatible with the NATO system. The generalized modern vision of the Armed Forces of Ukraine on the formation of the logistics system is published in:

- "Logistics forces will continue to develop in order to maintain armaments and military equipment, material resources and provide them to troops (forces), all components of the defense forces, as well as to create an effective system of infrastructure for troops (forces), which will ensure guaranteed performance of such basic tasks: real estate management, ensuring their settlement in permanent locations and during the performance of tasks in operations, maintenance of facilities and means of infrastructure, energy and utilities.

- Determining the needs and planning of logistic support will be entrusted to the logistics units (J, G, A, N, S-4) of the General Staff of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, commands of species, certain types of troops (forces), operational (air) commands and military units.

- The organization of logistical and infrastructure support will be entrusted to the Logistics Forces Command.

- In the medium and long term, units and subdivisions of logistical support will be consolidated into joint logistic support centers". It's difficult to disagree with the fact that the logistics management system must have a high combat readiness, survivability, resilience and provide the possibility of both centralized and decentralized management. So, the system of troops management automation is a set of the means of automation of management united by a uniform information space which provide support of decision-making, their delivery to executors and implementation of control over their

execution. Ultimately, the troops management automation system has to ensure that such operations are performed:

- collection, processing, analysis and evaluation of data on the location, condition, composition and stocks of material means of troops;

- reception, processing and display of commands and signals of combat control "from top to bottom" – from the highest body of military management;

- formation and issuance of confirmations of received signals and commands, exchange of formalized and informal information;

- management of troops in different states (in the course of daily activities, during the transition from peacetime to wartime and in wartime when solving operational tasks);

- automation of planning and management processes of the regular forces and means; - information protection and cyber security;

- integration of existing automation systems and tools. The skills of synchronization of each combat operations function with the general picture of operation in units of armed forces train during preparation, carrying out rehearsals of logistics within the limits of one or limited number of combat tasks. Such support rehearsals allow commanders to see the big picture and make decisions in real time. Their goal is to harmonize logistics with maneuvering plans, not to respond to changes in combat. One of the webinar speakers also noted that even when units adhere very closely to the concept of supply, the changes could place excessive numbers of troops and armaments in the way of movement and thus cause damage due to a lack of prior planning with support units. In practice, however, supplies often do not provide adequate combat support as a result of brigade support, an advanced support company (FSC) and a supported maneuvering battalion. In general, the

support rehearsal creates future decisions and causes changes in logistics requirements and solves the question of: who, what, when, where and how. Thus, based on the results of the support rehearsal, the units have to answer the following questions: What is the current status of logistics in each echelon? What are the problems with combat power that affects units? What are the ongoing supply arrangements in the echelon supervision units? What is the priority of support? What is the priority of the service and does it support the main efforts? What is the priority of supply? What is the priority of the care operation relative to weapons, medical assets etc.? When will the units need to be replenished and what are the signs for replenishment? What is the action plan for mass losses? Military experts are convinced that without proper logistics planning and synchronization for all teams, the battle will be lost. With which we completely agree too. Therefore, each unit has to integrate the rehearsal of the support according to its own timeline of continuous training, as well as the decision-making process and define standard operating procedures.

However, taking into account the current unstable military-political situation in Ukraine, it's appropriate to take into account the academic understanding and vision of the formation of a logistical support system for military operations readiness. First of all, it is worth paying attention to two key principles of logistics management – system-process and variable-situational principles, which are described in detail in [6, pp. 56–66]. In the monograph [3, pp. 185–189] a distinctive feature of the logistics economy is the focus on market segments, territories, regions and the country as a whole, not only it, but not only on enterprises, which reflects only the corporate goals of logistics services. The concept of economic space of logistics is revealed, which correlates with the concept of logistics system, the objects of

which are enterprises of different branches of economy, logistics capacities, transport communications, telecommunication systems, etc., These objects interact in accordance with the spatial (territorial) structure of the economy and the spatial (territorial) organization of economic entities, united by material and accompanying flows. Thus, according to Professor Grigorak M.Yu., it's important to study first the economic relations that arise in the economic space of logistics [3. pp. 185–189], and then work on the coordination of logistics flows. “In the theoretical and cognitive aspect of the logistics system” the Professor Alkema V.H. writes in his own monograph “it’s a subsystem of the economic system. Its feature at the macro level as an object of management is a set of interconnected and interacting logistics entities that develop the total resource potential, organized in the form of logistics flows by optimizing and streamlining them”. [2, p. 83]. This understanding of the logistics system as an economic space suggests that logistics is an element of the entity potential, namely its resource component. According to Professor Alkema V.G., the definition of the term “potential” is more widely used in relation to a particular type of resources or their combination, and two "resource" positions are distinguished:

1) potential as a set of resources without taking into account their relationships and participation in the production process is a generalized, collective characteristic of resources (quantity and quality of resources that a system has);

2) as a set of resources capable of producing a certain amount of material goods, as it characterizes the resources of production, their quantitative and qualitative parameters, which determine the maximum capacity of society to produce material goods at any given time. That is, it's a reflection of the ability to achieve high end results through the most efficient use of available resources. After

all, the concept of "resource" belongs to the elements of the operational process and is, in essence, opportunities to achieve goals that are determined by potential. Professor Alkema V.G. identifies two alternative scientist's views on the concept of resource potential: First, as a set of all resources of the enterprise, providing the opportunity to obtain the maximum economic effect at a given time; Secondly, as a system of resources, an interconnected set of material, energy, information tools, as well as the themselves workers, who use (or can use) them in the production of material goods and services.

The resource approach to the separation of logistics systems means that economic entities operate in conditions of limited resources and interact with each other in accordance with economic laws in order to: maximize the results of their activities (with a given amount of production resources to strive for maximum output); minimize the cost of production resources under a certain volume of production; optimize results (costs and results have to be in a certain optimal combination). The functioning of organizations – participants in the economic system of the highest order can't do without interaction with other organizations, components of market infrastructure. In particular, “economic and organizational relations of enterprises-producers of goods and services make it possible to carry out exchange processes and bring the manufactured products to the final consumer. Therefore, ... today it is not the availability of own resources in the enterprise that comes to the fore, but the opportunity and ability to use available external resources within the framework of mutually beneficial cooperation of companies in the supply chain”. [3, p. 186]. According to the author, the resource concept of the logistics system formation

involves the spatial component of the logistics system resources and the decomposition of their elements (on types and subtypes of resources by links of the logistics system). Logistics system resources include: tangible assets (fixed assets, current assets, investments) –

transaction costs; human resources (qualification, skills, activity / effectiveness) – partnership; intangible assets (strategic assets, own technologies, reputational assets, goodwill) – achieving a synergistic effect.

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